

A Study on Elementary Education Programme Operated Under Samagra Sikshya Abhiyan in Cuttack District

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Abstract:- The present study was conducted to find out the status of Elementary Education Programme in Cuttack. The objectives were to study the functions of Elementary Education operated under SSA in Cuttack district with reference to Physical facilities, Institutional inputs, Achievement, Community participation and Supervision and to study the challenges and find out different strategies for improving Elementary Education in Cuttack district. 20 numbers of schools, 40 teachers, 80 students and 40 parents were selected from urban and rural areas to conduct this study. The study revealed that there is a growth of SSA in Cuttack on the matter of various interventions. But all reported that the development of rural areas is far from satisfaction. From the data collected from the respondents may not be true but the findings as per the field visit, taking responses from the higher authority, public and from the secondary data available the investigator come to know the real picture of the progress of SSA activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

In India, education has been ensured as fundamental right of the children under 6-14 age group in order to boost the mission of Universalisation of Elementary Education (UEE). A centrally sponsored holistic approach SSA has been launched during November; 2000. The scheme covers the entire nation meeting with the needs of 192 million children in 11 lakh habitations through 8.5 lakh existing schools and 33 lakh teachers. As a people's mass movement for qualitative and quantitative expansion and improvement on the line of District Primary Education Programme (DPEP), SSA has a long road to contribute India's socio-economic development. Really India has been considerably developing in the field of education since Independence. In spite of spectacular initiatives, plans and programmes to pace the elementary education up to the international standard it has been facing many challenges. It has been experienced that education is the most suitable panacea to face the modern dynamic challenges of the world in which elementary stage is the base the entire superstructure. It was a turning chapter in the history of education when the National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986 and Programme of Action

(1992) took important policy decisions to augment the pace of UEE through widespread programmes. Again it got an International acknowledgement at Education for All (EFA) in 1991. Further in 1994; DPEP an experiment on quantitative expansion and qualitative improvement in the field of UEE played a vital role in cementing the comprehensive and compulsory education. The success of DPEP opened a new framework that is SSA to enlarge the National objective. The UEE, a revolution in Indian education when the long cherished dream, "The Fundamental Right to Education" under article 21(A) announced under the constitutional amendment by the Government of India (GOI), SSA became a basic to implement the programmes related to UEE within a target time frame. But there are so many challenges to realize the big mission of UEE through SSA in the country. Especially in Odisha, it has to face many hurdles to achieve the goal. This study is about the growth and status of Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) in realizing the goal of the nation, UEE in Cuttack district of Odisha. The focus is on what has been happening in the district in regards to SSA and what different authorities, the teachers' community members, parents, students think about the SSA. It is an assessment of the programmes of the Government, the State as well as the Centre, and the successes and failures as seen through the stakeholders, parents, students of elementary education.

II. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Elementary schools are functioning under SSA and are managed by state government. Most of the dropouts are found in government schools which are running under SSA. The probable reasons for the non-enrolment, irregular retention and school dropout might be due to the poverty, migration of parents, lack of positive parental attitude for studies of their children, frequent physical sickness because of malnutrition and lack of better hygiene, lack of awareness of parents, broken families, and domestic work, sibling care and other compelling reasons for the children which made them to remain out of school system. In view of the above discussions, the present study seeks to address itself to the following questions.

- Is there any change revealed in the school environment, physical facilities and achievement of learners due to SSA at elementary stage of Cuttack district?
- Whether the change in the process of administration and management helped in bringing about qualitative and quantitative improvement in elementary education?
- Is SSA helped in meeting the problems and challenges of the educational institutions?
- Is there any improvement witnessed in the enrolment, student’s study habits and participation in classroom activities due to SSA?

In order to seek the answers to the above research questions, the investigators thought it worthwhile to undertake the present study entitled as “**A Study on Elementary Education Programme Operated under Samagra Sikshya Abhiyan in Cuttack District**”.

➤ *Operational Definitions:*

- **Elementary Education:** The education that is given to the children of age group 6-14 years from class I to VIII including primary and upper Primary level is termed as elementary education in India.
- **Samagra Sikshya Abhiyan:** Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is Government of India’s flagship programme for achievement of Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) in a time bound manner, as mandated by 86th amendment to the Constitution of India making free and compulsory Education to the Children of 6-14 years age group, a Fundamental Right.

➤ *Objectives of the Study:*

The objectives of the study were:

- To Study the functioning of Elementary Education operated under SSA in Cuttack district with reference to Physical facilities, Institutional inputs, Achievement, Community participation and Supervision.
- To study the challenges and find out different strategies for improving Elementary Education in Cuttack district.

➤ *Delimitations of the Study:*

- The study was confined to the Elementary schools operated by the SSA of Cuttack district only.
- The study was conducted in 20 SSA schools of Cuttack district only.

III. METHODOLOGY

Keeping in view of the nature of the problem the investigator followed Descriptive Survey design. This study is based on the interview method. The investigator paid a visit to teachers, students and parents. He also had interaction with them through face-to-face mode i.e interviews to elicit necessary information for the study.

➤ *Population and Sample*

The area of the study was delimited to Cuttack district. In this study both rural and urban areas were taken into consideration. 20 numbers of schools, 40 teachers, 80 students and 40 parents were selected from urban and rural areas to conduct this study.

➤ *Instruments:*

- **Questionnaire:** Four sets of questionnaire were developed. One questionnaire for sampled teachers.
- **Interview schedule:** There were two sets of Interview scheduled developed for the purpose. One for student and another for parents related to school.

➤ *Preparation of Tools*

The draft of the tools developed by the investigators were put before with five experts from RNIASE and DIET, Cuttack, Pedagogy coordinator of the district and Research scholars of DIET, Cuttack.

➤ *Procedure of Data Collection*

With the prior permission from District Education Officer and heads of the institutions the data was collected. Adequate rapport was established through personal contact with Teachers, Students and parents. The purpose of the study was explained to them. The questionnaires were individually administered to the subjects. Respondents were assured of confidentiality of their responses.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Results obtained on administration of tools on the subjects need systematic analysis and interpretation to get the answers to the research questions.

➤ *Perception of Teachers on interventions provided by SSA*

Entire success of SSA will go to teachers for their sincerity and dedication on duty. For the present study 80 teachers were selected from 4 blocks to assess the effect of SSA for fulfilling the goals of UEE in Cuttack district. They were provided a questionnaire to fill up and also interviewed to get qualitative data.

➤ *Personal information*

The teachers were asked to give their qualification and experience and the data is produced here for analyses in tables

Table-1 Experience Configuration of sample Teachers (No.40)

Particulars	value
Teaching experience mean in year	16.4
Teaching experience range in year	04-25

It can be said from the table 1 about the teaching experience of the sample teachers that their teaching experience mean value is 16.4 and range is 4-25 years. It shows that their experience is good enough to teach properly according to the pedagogic interventions in the classroom. in Cuttack there are

different category teachers area teaching. The new teachers are highly skilled and take interest and zeal to teach properly. But in rural areas they give less interest in teaching. Hence it can be suggested that teachers should be accountable and develop dedication on their prime duty of teaching for giving justice to the students and society.

Table 2 Qualification configuration of sample Teachers (No.40)

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Secondary	02	05
Higher secondary	20	50
Graduation (ARTS)	06	15
Graduation (Science)	04	10
M.A	06	15
M. Sc.	02	05
Professional qualification (D. El. Ed)	22	55
B. Ed	16	40
M. Ed	02	05

Table 2 shows that there are no untrained teachers in Cuttack district. Most of the teachers belong to Arts background and there are teachers completing higher qualification in the district. Really teachers with good academic and professional qualification are the assets for the society and nation. High qualified youths are seen in the teaching profession is a good indication for the success of UEE mission.

➤ *Incentive available*

Various incentives are provided to the teachers time to time. This is presented by the sample teachers in the following way.

Table 3 Interventions provided to school by Teachers (No.40)

SL. No	Types of Interventions for school	% of availability
01	Guide book	100
02	Incentives for teaching	00
03	Financial assistance	00
04	Training to teacher	75
05	Grant for TLM	100

The table 3 shows that 100% teachers are provided guide books (Sikshya Sathi), Samadhana, different modules for teaching effectively. They also receive 100% TLM grants of Rs.500 per year to purchase and prepare teaching learning materials for classroom teaching. Teachers perceived that they have got 75% trainings from different levels and still some teachers require training in some specific subjects. No such provisions are there for financial assistance and incentive for teaching. Sometimes prizes are distributed for good teachers' at district and state level. So it is suggested that teacher's skill has to be highlighted in different meeting, function. Incentive

should be provided in an example basis for others. Teachers teaching in tribal and rural areas must get some special allowance as a morale booster. They have reported that they have received TLM training once in the past three year which is insufficient. It is suggested that special workshop should be organized in a cluster for teachers once in a year and there must be sufficient storage provision for TLM in every schools. While preparing TLM the respondent viewed that they make discussion with Headmaster, other colleagues and students on preparation and use of TLM. Sometimes they jointly prepare TLM with the help of students. In 20-30% schools there is proper provision of TLM banks in active stage observed by the investigator.

➤ *Role in MDM*

Teachers play an important role in MDM programme in the school. They reported that they supervise the MDM distribution, taste the quality of the food, present during MDM distribution, observing cleanliness of the dining space and reporting attendance and problems found in the distribution of MDM.

➤ *Perception of students on interventions provided by SSA*

Students are the destiny maker of the nation. All the activities are undertaken by focusing the students in our schools. Students are the nucleus in the entire interventions of the SSA. Taking the importance of students, the investigator included students (No.80) in the present study and collected their views on the functioning of elementary education under SSA in Cuttack district. 20 schools were selected and Focused Group Discussion was conducted by taking 20 groups of students. Their collective views were collected under 5 items such as personal information, regularity, Study assistance, and infrastructural facilities. Their collective and group responses are analyzed in this section.

➤ *Personal information*

For the study some personal data were collected from the sample students. Under 4 groups on the basis of class below V, class VI, VII, VIII was fixed.

Table 4 Qualification configuration by students (No.80)

Class of Students	Frequency	Percentage
Primary	20	25
Class VI	20	25
Class VII	20	25
Class VIII	20	25
Total	80	100

From the table 4, it can be pointed that 20 students of class V, VI, VII and VIII were randomly selected for the study. They reported that their all brothers and sisters are in government schools in different class.

➤ *Regularity:***Table 5 Regularity of the teacher perceived by Students (No.80)**

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Regularly coming	58	72.5
Irregular	16	20
Cannot say	06	07.5
Total	80	100

From the table 5, it is seen that 58% support teacher's regularity and only 16% viewed on irregularity. So it reveals that still some teachers are irregular mainly found in remote schools where supervision is held occasionally. It is suggested that proper monitoring and exchange of teacher can solve this situation. They express their inability to complain against irregularity of the teacher. On punishment following views were collected.

➤ *Facilities available:*

Students responded that they get facilities like MDM, Books, Uniform, and Kit bag at primary level. But uniform is not available for general boys. The government should provide uniform to all irrespective of difference. Play materials are scanty as viewed by most of the students.

➤ *Study Assistance:*

In some cases urban students are guided by their parents but it is rare in rural areas. Many parents prefer private tuition in village for giving extra guidance for the children. In some occasions competitions are organized in schools as perceived by most of the students. It is suggested that teachers should give a look into non scholastic areas of the learners. Only some students participate in different competitions.

➤ *Infrastructural Facilities*

On the question of toilet facilities boys don't use toilets in most of the schools due to lack of facility of cleaning. In most cases girls use toilet and in some schools toilets are in unhygienic condition. Students agreed that they participate actively in beautification of the school. They also viewed that only some teachers (30-40%) come to class with TLM and aids. They feel proud as a student of Government school as they are getting free education not giving burden to their parents. It is realized that SSA interventions have made good standard in physical infrastructure but if quality will controlled students will get maximum benefit. A joint effort of all stake holders is an urgent need of the hour.

➤ *Perception Parents on Interventions Provided by SSA:*

Parents play an effective role in making SSA successful. It is seen due to lack of awareness and interest they do not take their responsibilities seriously. Therefore in the present investigation views of community members are collected through an interview schedule. Sufficient rapport was provided to the respondent to give their open views and perception on 7

different items on the effect of SSA in their school. Their responses are analyses in this section.

➤ *Personal Information.*

In the beginning some personal information was collected this includes qualification, occupation and preference of school. Following responses were collected

Table 06 Qualification configuration by sample members (No.40)

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Below secondary	12	30
Secondary	12	30
Higher secondary	08	20
Degree	05	12.5
Higher qualification	03	07.5
Total	40	100

Table 06 shows that most of the members and parents in SSA related schools are less qualified. Hence this is the main criteria for not understanding the manifold interventions provided by the government to the school. Parent's higher education is a positive factor for success of SSA.

Table 07 Preference of school by Members (No.40)

Preference of school	Frequency	Percentage
SSA or Government	28	70
Non SSA or Private	12	30
Total	40	100

On the question of preference of school for children they supported SSA school as stated in table 07. The frequency and percentage was 70. It can be analyses that in most of the cases rural and tribal parents prefer SSA school as it is totally free and not a burden on them.

➤ *Facility available*

On the question of facilities members supported the interventions for their children. They agreed that Girls, SC, ST children at Upper primary level gets scholarship by the government. Books are received by students properly. No one ask for money on any occasion as viewed by the respondents.

➤ *Students' Enrolment, attendance and dropout:*

From the perception of parents it is shown that they can discuss on the attendance of the school with teachers and heads. In case of students absence matter is discussed in different meetings. Through mobilization drop out can be checked sufficient co curricular activities and attractive classroom teaching can improve regularity of the students as viewed by them.

➤ Evaluation

On evaluation they perceived that 4 formative, unit test, 1 half yearly and one annual examination held in each session. They want that evaluation system should be strict and it require reform.

➤ Role of School Committee

There are different types of membership provision in SSA system. In the present investigation the sample members are categorized in the following way.

Table 8 Configuration of Sample Members (No.100)

Members	Frequency	Percentage
PTA/Parents	20	50
MTA/Parents	20	50
Total	100	100

Table 8 shows that most of the respondents in the study are PTA and MTA members (parents) comprising 50% and 50% respectively. They have attended training, SAHAYOGA and it was helpful for them in knowing different provisions of SSA. On some special case they are also provided training at BRCC and CRCC level. They were provided Rs 30 with a lunch per day for attending training. In every month The SMC calls meeting for strategic discussion on school matter. MTA and PTA meeting held once in every 3 and 6 months.

➤ Participation in School Activities

Table 9 Role in school activity by Sample members (No.40)

Statement	Frequency	Percentage
Active participation in school activity	26	65
In active in school activities	14	35
Total	40	100

The table 9 shows that 65% parent and members participate in school activities actively and the percentage of inactive participants found in the study 35%. They support school in preparation of TLM (22%), helping teachers (8%), participate in cultural programmes (94%), beautification of the school (47%) as per the perception of the respondents. They suggested that proper parent counseling, active teacher's role and qualitative teaching will improve the standard of SSA and student's real knowledge and skill should be improved for their better future..

V. MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

From the perceptions of the respondents, it is found that there is a growth of SSA in Cuttack on the matter of various interventions. But all reported that the development of rural areas is far from satisfaction. From the data collected from the respondents may not be true but the findings as per the field visit, taking responses from the higher authority, public and

from the secondary data available the investigator come to know the real picture of the progress of SSA activities these are listed below.

- Student' absenteeism is found in rural area more than the urban area due to involvement of children in domestic work and involve in parental occupation.
- Maintenance of MDM as a burden for teacher and teachers and head masters face difficulty to focus on teaching.
- Teacher resides at distance place. Residence facility is required in cluster for regularity.
- Text books are not supplied in time i.e. in the month of April, the starting point of an academic session and old books are not sufficient.
- In rural pockets 30% irregular teachers are there which shows a big problem in quality in SSA.
- For increasing enrolment of girls, SC/ST children some innovative steps have been taken at block level such as parents' counseling, vivid discussion with SMC/PTA/MTA meeting , linking CRCC to the low enrolment schools.
- No specific training has been provided for TLM to teachers for which a workshop should be organized at cluster level for better preparation of TLM.
- Pedagogy training is given to the newly recruited teachers and special training has provided to Gana Sikshyaka (GS).
- Topics discussed in the SMC meeting are regarding students' regularity, teachers' regularity, maintenance of MDM, Utilization of governments fund, analysis of assessment, school cleanliness and beautification etc.
- Government grants are received for SIG, TLM, Uniform and Repairing and maintenance of the building and utilized properly.
- It has been observed that literacy percentage has affected the enrolment ratio of different blocks of study area. In the blocks with higher percentage of literacy rate, the enrolment ratio is also higher in comparison to the block where the ratio is low.
- In all the blocks of the study the enrolment percentage is more than 95%.
- SSA interventions have significant effect on enrolment of children
- Under SSA uniforms have been distributed freely to girls who resulted in enhancing their enrolment in schools.
- School building, additional classroom have affected in increasing the enrolment ratio.
- It has been observed that after SSA, spectacular growth of infrastructural facilities has occurred in schools which have also become helpful in increasing enrolment ratio of the study area.
- Due to organization of MTA,PTA under SSA the enrolment ratio has also increased
- The role of SMC has a positive factor for the increasing enrolment of the children.
- Appointment of the teaching staff as per the norm of SSA has a positive impact on the enrolment of children.

- Enrolment of girl child has increased due to construction of toilet in the school.
- Due to free text books distribution there is increasing of student enrolment under SSA.
- Training of community members has a positive impact on the growth of enrolment of children.
- Under SSA special infrastructure facilities has increased the enrolment of learner with special need.
- SSA has significant impact on the retention of the children
- It has been observed that the rate of retention has increased due to MDM in rural blocks.
- Due to parent's involvement and awareness the rate of retention has increased.
- Due to involvement of SMC/PTA/MTA there is a growth of the retention of children in schools.
- Due to free text books and uniform there is a growth of retention in Cuttack district.
- Child friendly environment and punishment free system increases retention of the children after SSA.
- Implementation of SSA in Cuttack district has significant effect on achievement of learner in primary school.
- Due to appointment of sufficient number of teachers and lady teachers in elementary level under SSA has resulted in increasing achievement level of the children.
- Activity based learning has a greater role on achievement level of the student.
- It has been observed that availability of teaching equipment and TLM has affected the achievement of the learners.
- Achievement of the learner has also affected by the involvement of community members and parents involvement.

VI. CONCLUSION

Another problematic field is found with teacher. Teachers' absence from their school reduces teaching hours. To improve schooling quality, there is a need to increase teachers' teaching hours. To increase teachers' teaching hours, there is a need to reduce suitably the duration of in-service training being imparted to teachers every year under Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA). This is because hardly any substitute teacher is posted in school when a teacher is under in-service training. Teachers were engaged in nonprofessional work. Teachers should not be engaged in non-professional duties. This measure would further improve teachers' teaching hours in schools. Teachers should be dedicated enough to prove as a beacon light for the education and society. Right attitude and enthusiasm in all activity with interest can make SSA a successful weapon to curb all maladies.

Educational authorities must plan properly for proper implementation of SSA interventions in the target area and authority. Books should be provided in time so that authority at grass root level will not face difficulties. Curriculum revision, new training module, innovations in teaching and research programmes should be made focus area. Sufficient and timely

allocation fund for conducting different work should be done before hand. The problems on SSA is not confined in Cuttack district only but it is the problem of all district. A look into the study can help everybody to get an insight on the functioning of the SSA and solutions for future course of action.

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